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CO₂ Utilization through Production of Carbonated Salt Nanoparticles in a Rotating Packed Bed

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Abstract

Creating new value chains by CO₂ utilization will assist the wide proliferation of carbon capture and utilization technologies (CCU). Captured CO₂ can be utilized as raw material in the production of value-added nano-structured products like carbonate particles, i.e. precipitated calcium carbonate (nano-PCC). In this work we discuss our experiments for the synthesis of nano-PCC in a pilot plant that was developed by our team in CERTH. The pilot plant employs a rotating packed bed (RPB) to perform direct aqueous carbonation of Ca(OH)₂ suspensions with a stream of pure CO₂. The carbonation is performed at mild conditions (atmospheric pressure and temperatures up to 60 °C). The precursor Ca(OH)₂ is suspended in deionized water (10 – 50 g/L) without any additives. Important operating parameters like precursor concentration, gas and liquid flow rate, L/G ratio and rotating speed were varied, creating several sets of operating conditions. The process performance was evaluated based on three key criteria: reaction time needed until complete conversion of the precursor, particle size and CO₂ utilization efficiency. We also propose a model that was developed to predict the process behavior under different designs and operating conditions and was validated with the actual experimental data. We achieved nano-PCC monodisperses of minimum average crystallite size of 45 nm and primary particle size as low as 181 nm. The reaction time was halved (-49 %) by adjusting the flowrates and rotating speed compared to the base case. The RPB enabled important acceleration of nano-PCC crystallization compared to conventional equipment. The modelling results showed good agreement with the experimentally acquired ΔCO₂, with a maximum mean absolute deviation of 9.4%.

Keywords: CO₂ utilization; Rotating Packed Beds; reactive precipitation; CaCO₃; rate-based model

1. Introduction

CO₂ utilization is required to close the carbon cycle and achieve circularity in industry and will possibly become a determining factor to assure the economic competitiveness of capture systems. Finding ways to transform CO₂ from a discarded waste stream to a useful raw material towards high-value products could prove beneficial especially for inherent CO₂ emitters in hard-to-abate sectors [1], [2]. Transforming a captured CO₂ stream into marketable, nano-scaled carbonated minerals with the aid of process intensification equipment is demonstrated in this work to be a valid

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route. The approach of slurry carbonation, the simplest route there is, in RPBs paves the road for improved and intensified mass production of nano – precipitated calcium carbonate and hydromagnesite.

Conventionally, PCC is produced in bubble columns or continuously stirred batch reactors, which introduce the bottleneck of time-consuming procedures during the production stage. Intrinsic shortcomings of such setups include long processing times and poor controllability over product properties, while serious mass transfer limitations mandate large equipment sizes and harsh synthesis conditions [3], [4]. These challenges can be addressed with Rotating Packed Bed (RPB) reactors [5], where a high gravity environment develops due to the centrifugal acceleration of the packing material. This forces the liquid phase to flow as thin films and minute droplets, enhancing the gas – liquid contact area and therefore the mass transfer [6]. This leads to potential equipment size reductions of up to 10 times in comparison to conventional equipment [7], [8].

RPBs have been applied previously in the synthesis of metal oxide nanoparticles [9], [10]. This experience has shown that RPBs represent potentially suitable equipment for the intensification of the carbonation process targeting reactive crystallization for nanostructured products. However, to our knowledge, there are very few studies dealing with the production of high-quality nano-PCC. Most studies refer to the carbonation of waste streams, like blast oxygen furnace slags [11], calcium-rich wastewater [12] etc., that inevitably lead to CaCO_3 products of low purity and increased particle size, above the micro-scale. The existing reports on $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ carbonation present little detail on the technical specifications of the employed equipment and process design, that renders the reported results unsuitable for the validation of a new model. Such models are useful tools to predict and optimize the behavior of the reactive crystallization process in RPBs.

Nomenclature

CCU	carbon capture and utilization
PCC	precipitated calcium carbonate
RPB	rotating packed bed
ΔCO_2	utilization efficiency of CO_2
$m_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}}$	mass flow rate of CO_2 fed in the RPB
$m_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{out}}$	mass flow rate of CO_2 leaving the RPB
ODE	ordinary differential equation
MAD	mean absolute deviation
KPI	key performance indicator

2. Experimental

2.1. Pilot plant and process description

An aqueous suspension of the precursor is pumped from the reactant tank to the center of a torus-shaped packing through in the RPB. The RPB is positioned vertically. As the packing rotates, the liquid is distributed radially and wets the packing with thin films and droplets. An external circulator provides the necessary heat to control the temperature of the liquid (water used as heating medium). Pure CO_2 is introduced from a pressurized cylinder via a mass flow controller from a separate inlet on the RPB casing. Physically absorbed in the aqueous medium, the CO_2 produces carbonate and bicarbonate anions that react with calcium (magnesium) cations that leach due to hydrolysis of the precursor, producing nuclei that grew under the influence of heat and time. The unreacted gas leaves the reactor from a port on the casing. After visiting a knock-out drum, its flow rate is measured with a gas flow meter. The liquid flows into the product tank which serves as a temporary storage site and as an equilibrators of flow before recycling towards the reactant tank. The liquid is circulated until the pH is neutralized, meaning that complete consumption of precursor is achieved. Possible sampling points are denoted as S1, S2 and S3 in Figure 1a. In this case liquid samples were collected from S3. Important technical details of the pilot plant are presented in Table 1. There is an option for

counter-current or co-current operation. In this case the RPB was operated co-currently. A drawing of a concurrent RPB reactor is presented in Figure 1b.

Figure 1. Pilot-scale process incorporating a RPB reactor for the production of nanoparticles by suspension carbonation (simplified process flow sheet)

2.2. Model structure

The modelling of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ suspension carbonation using a pure CO_2 stream for the production of nano-sized PCC in an RPB reactor was developed with a first principles approach. The model was based on Higbie's penetration theory, while both the kinetics of the reactive carbonation and the mass transfer phenomena were also integrated. Figure 2 shows the algorithmic steps followed by the model for co-current operation. The model can also simulate counter-current operation with minor modifications. At first, the required parameters are initialized (e.g., reactor dimensions and specifications, suspension and gas composition and properties). The model solves an algebraic equation system and subsequently an ordinary differential equation (ODE) system. The solution sequence is one-dimensional and starts from the inner radius of the reactor, gradually moving toward the outer radius. A detailed presentation of the proposed model is shown in [13].

Figure 2. Algorithmic flowsheet for co-current operation

2.3. Materials and methods

A $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ powder of 93 % purity, median size of 88.64 μm , specific surface area of 14.5 m^2/g (provided by CAO HELLAS) was used as precursor. $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ suspensions were prepared with deionised water (30 L) and immediately loaded in the pilot plant. The suspension was heated and circulated in the system under N_2 atmosphere until reaching the desired temperature. Then CO_2 gas was introduced with a controlled flowrate marking the start of an experiment. The progress of reaction was monitored by liquid sampling and off-line pH measurement (Metrohm 906 Titrando) in regular time periods. Over time the pH was reduced from 12 to 6.5, with neutralization indicating the completion of the reaction. Finally, samples were collected, then filtrated, rinsed and air-dried overnight at 105 $^\circ\text{C}$. X-Ray diffraction analysis was applied on the produced powder for structure identification and crystallite size calculation (BRUKER/D8 Advance D8 Advance Diffractometer, Cu K_α radiation, scanning range 5-80 $^\circ/0.04^\circ$). The crystallite size was calculated based on the Debye-Scherrer equation. The purity was specified by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) (LECO TGA 701, 0-960 $^\circ\text{C}$). The powder was re-suspended in water for PSD analysis (Laser Scattering Particle Size Distribution Analyzer LA-960/HORIBA). The particle morphology was observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (JEOL 6300, Oxford ISIS-2000), and the primary particle size distribution was measured with the tool Image J[®].

Three key performance indicators (KPIs) were defined for the evaluation of the processes' performance: 1) reaction time for complete consumption of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, 2) particle and crystallite size and 3) ΔCO_2 in the pilot plant reactor (Equation (1)). The operating parameters of suspension flow rate, gas flow rate and rotating speed were varied independently in an effect – response study, to explore the effect of their variation on the three KPIs. The experiments were performed with a variety of operating conditions including a 10 – 50 g/L precursor concentration, a 3 – 9 L/min gas flow rate, a 3.43 – 4.75 L/min suspension flow rate, 600 – 1800 rpm rotating speed and at 60 – 65 %.

$$\Delta\text{CO}_2 = \frac{m_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}} - m_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{out}}}{m_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The data acquired during these experiments were subsequently used for the validation of the proposed model. The model was tested for the experiments running on batch mode, considering as input the feed from a tank with predetermined quantity of suspension in each experiment. The reactor dimensions and operating conditions are governed by the experiments, and the suspension properties inside the tank are altered with time according to the model output.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Experimental results

Calcite was identified as the main phase in all synthesized materials with XRD. The particle morphology (Figure 3) is typical for calcite and agrees with other references [14]. SEM images reveal clusters of smaller, submicron, aggregated particles. Aggregation could not be avoided, given that no particle stabilizers/surfactants were applied post-synthetically. The purity of the nano-PCC particles ranged between 93.2 - 98.1 %. A likely source of impurity could be the existence of small cores of unreacted $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ within the calcite matrix, that convert to CaO upon heating above 400 $^\circ\text{C}$.

An average crystallite size of 31 – 62 nm was calculated via Debye-Scherrer equation depending on the operating parameters. Processing SEM images with Image J[®] we measured a mean particle size of 181 – 443, with the particle size distributions span again depending on the operating parameters. The recorded particle size for most of the samples was smaller compared to other studies, that employ either RPB reactors [11] or conventional equipment [15]. PSD analysis on resuspended powders showed aggregate sizes of 2.5 – 3.5 μm , confirming the SEM observations. All powdered products exhibited monodisperses.

Figure 3: Representative PCC powder synthesized in the RPB. Magnification: $\times 20,000$. Bar length: 1 μm

For suspensions of equal precursor concentration, i.e. 10 g/L or 30 g/L the reaction time could be varied within $\pm 45\%$ depending on the selected combination of operating parameters. An average processing time per gram of precursor was calculated to be approximately 0.08 min/g, which is about an order of magnitude lower compared to studies dealing with the carbonation of waste streams in RPBs [11], [16]. An indicative example is presented in Figure 4a, where the reaction time is seen to be shortened significantly when the operating speed is increased from 600 to 1800 rpm, because the mass transfer rate increases. Specifically, the reaction time needed to fully consume 900 g of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ was approximately halved to 38 min (-49%), when the gas flow rate was appropriately adjusted, with all other operating parameters unchanged. These remarks seem to agree with other RPB related studies [17]–[19]. The effect of rotating speed is more pronounced when L/G ratios below unity are applied. As the L/G ratio increases the effect becomes milder, such that increasing the rotating speed does not offer any visible improvement.

With the RPB reactor we were able to avoid operating with a high excess of CO_2 . The system could be operated at a $[\text{CO}_2 : \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2]$ ratio very close to stoichiometry and at atmospheric pressure. This is not the case when carbonation is performed in stirred vessels. Because of the relatively slow kinetics of some of the parallel reactions (dissolution of Ca^{2+} cations) and because of gradual pulp thickening that hinders the physical absorption of CO_2 as neutralization is approached, reactive crystallization in stirred reactors is commonly performed with a high CO_2 excess, to achieve supersaturation and to push the carbonation forward. This usually results in very low conversion rates of CO_2 .

Figure 4: a) Time needed until pH neutralization of a 30 L batch of aqueous $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ suspension with 30 g/L concentration at 55 °C depending on the experimental conditions (Liquid flowrate: 3.43 L/min, Gas flowrate: 6 L/min) and b) CO_2 utilization efficiency depending on the [L/G] ratio and rotating speed

In the RPB the overall utilization efficiency of CO_2 (ΔCO_2) was higher than 94 %, meaning that over 94 % of the incoming CO_2 flowrate was absorbed and transformed into PCC during an experiment (Figure 4b). We observed that an increased [L/G] ratio had a positive effect on ΔCO_2 regardless of the rotating speed. This effect was stronger when

operating at low – medium rotating speed (600, 1000 rpm). The system exhibited a consistently high ΔCO_2 when operating at high speed (1800 rpm), regardless of the corresponding [L/G] ratio.

In general, we observed that the variation of the operating parameters (gas flow rate, liquid flow rate and rotating speed) resulted in trade-offs among the employed KPIs. For example, an increased gas flow rate may correspond to reduced residence time of the gas phase, thus negatively affecting the capture efficiency and reaction yield, and, simultaneously, may contribute to an increased overall mass transfer rate, which accelerates the crystallization process. Specifically, we observed a triple trade-off between reaction time – product purity – capture efficiency. At low speeds (600 rpm) the gravitational acceleration was relatively low and, most likely, not sufficient for handling high liquid or gas flowrates. This combination of operating parameters was responsible for unwanted maldistribution phenomena that reduced the gas – liquid interface (contact area) hindering the mass-transfer rate. This resulted in longer reaction time, lower ΔCO_2 and/or lower product purity. When the gravitational acceleration was sufficient (1800 rpm), the same combination of gas and liquid flowrates was handled effectively, due to improved interfacial contact and possibly reduced mass transfer resistance. This is in line with other studies published literature [20].

3.2. Modelling results

Figure 5 presents a typical case of model-experiment comparison for the denoted operating conditions. The trade-offs of the model and the experimental data exhibit good agreement. Mean absolute deviation (MAD) was used for the quantitative assessment of the model validation. The results showed that MAD ranges between 5.7 % and 9.4 % for all the tested experiments, highlighting the reliability of the predictive model. The validation of the model is considered successful, as the maximum MAD is 9.4 % and the trade-offs of the experimental data are also followed by the model.

MAD = 5.7 %

Figure 5: Typical trade-off between model and experimental. The letter G stands for gas flowrate and L stands for liquid flowrate.

4. Conclusions

PCC nanoparticles of crystallite size of 45 nm were successfully produced via carbonation of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ suspensions in a pilot scale RPB under mild conditions, without additives. No post-synthesis modifications were applied on the dried powders. Evidently, the RPB enabled important shortening of reaction time, overcoming limitations caused by the slow dissolution rate of Ca^{2+} cations and the lower solubility of CO_2 at higher suspension viscosities when approaching neutralization. The CO_2 capture efficiency was higher than 95 %. Conditions leading to the reduction of particle size were associated with the co-existence of high flowrates of suspension (4.75 L/min), high speed (1800 rpm) and lower gas flowrate (3 L/min). The validation of the proposed model with experimental data was successful. The model results expressed maximum MAD of 9.4 %, indicating good fitting to the experimental data.

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